

DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND PHYSICAL CULTURE - AS A FACTOR OF PHYSICAL MATURITY

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ABSTRACT: One of the important tasks in the harmonious development of physical and intellectual resources of young people is the extensive use of the opportunities of the basics of physical culture, physical education and physical development. This article provides theoretical information on the basics of physical culture, physical education and physical development.

KEYWORDS: culture, physical culture, education, physical education, ability, sports, physical training, coach.

РАЗВИТИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ- КАК ФАКТОР ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ЗРЕЛОСТИ

Аннотация: Одной из важных задач в гармоничном развитии физических и интеллектуальных ресурсов молодежи является широкое использование возможностей основ физической культуры, физического воспитания и физического развития. В данной статье представлена теоретическая информация по основам физической культуры, физическому воспитанию и физическому развитию.

Ключевые слова: культура, физическая культура, образование, физическое воспитание, способности, спорт, физическая подготовка, тренер

INTRODUCTION

The modern broad concept of "physical education" refers to the organic component of General Education - an educational, pedagogical process aimed at mastering by a person the personal values of Physical Culture. In other words, the purpose of physical education is the formation of the physical culture of the individual, that is, the aspect that contributes to the realization of the biological and spiritual possibilities of Human general culture. Physical education, whether we understand it or not, begins from the first days after the birth of a new person.

It is well known that culture is the creative activity of man. The basis and content of the cultural and psychological process of development of "culture" is, first of all, the development of physical and intellectual abilities of man, his moral and aesthetic qualities. In our society, large-scale work is carried out to create a healthy lifestyle, create modern conditions for regular physical culture and mass sports of the population, especially the younger generation, strengthen confidence in the will, strength and capabilities of young people through sports competitions, courage and patriotism, devotion to their homeland, development feelings of the people, as well as on the systematic organization of the selection of talented athletes among young people, as well as on the further development of physical culture and mass sports.

Upbringing is an organized pedagogical process for the purposeful improvement of the individual, which allows a regular and systematic impact on the pupil's personality. It is very important to organize the life and activities of students in a pedagogically correct way in the educational process. Physical education is a pedagogical process aimed at the morphological and functional improvement of the human body, the formation and improvement of basic motor skills, abilities, knowledge associated with them, which are important for his life.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Physical culture, physical education and sports are important factors not only in physical but also in spiritual development. It heals the will, teaches to strive for a clear goal, to endure difficulties with endurance and perseverance. It instills in the human heart a sense of confidence, pride and pride in victory .

The main indicators of the state of physical culture in society:

- the level of human health and physical development;
- the level of use of physical culture in the field of upbringing and education, in production, in everyday life, in the structure of leisure;
- the nature of the physical education system, the development of mass sports, the perfection of sports, and so on.

The essence of upbringing is different in each period, and its content stems from social goals. Although the idea of upbringing is expressed differently, but the nature of the direction and the object are expressed in unity.

In society, physical culture is the property of the people and is an important means of educating a new person who combines spiritual wealth, moral purity, and physical perfection. It relies on increasing the social and labor activity of people, the economic efficiency of production, the movement of physical culture, the multifaceted activities of state and public organizations in the field of physical and sports. People's physical culture is part of its history. The concept of physical culture undoubtedly includes all that is created by people's consciousness, talent, sewing, all that reflects its spiritual essence, its attitude to the world, nature, man and human relations.

It is time to develop physical culture, personality, the "technique" of its implementation in practice and to understand the decisive concept in the physical culture and upbringing of the younger generation, to form and strengthen consciousness based on deep knowledge and beliefs and constant care. The peculiarity of physical education as a social phenomenon is that it can serve mainly in society as a means of developing a person's physical abilities and at the same time have a strong influence on his spiritual maturity. This feature is a special feature of physical education that is applied to all equally. But in the real life of society, there is no physical education at all outside of specific historical conditions.

The task of physical education is solved so successfully that if participants consciously understand exercise or if they are interested in sports and take a creative approach, they will have to rely on general specialized knowledge for the correct formation of motor skills and functional abilities.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In each socio-economic formation develops a specific historical type of physical education.

Physical training. There are three main directions in physical education, and human physical education is carried out on the basis of these frameworks. They are general physical training, professional physical training, sports training.

Vocational physical training is a process of physical education aimed at preparing for a specialized, specific type of work and defense activities. It mainly uses types of exercise that are close to the profession or occupation.

The use of occupationally oriented physical training tools accelerates the process of acquisition of labor skills, increases labor productivity, improves the body's resistance to harmful factors of the external environment.

Sports training represents a special direction in physical education. The task of this is to ensure that a person achieves high results in a chosen sport.

CONCLUSION

Physical education is an integral part of general culture. It not only improves health but also eliminates some congenital and acquired diseases.

In conclusion, the quality of physical culture and physical education will increase if all types of physical development of students, improving sports skills, further improving the work of teachers and coaches, as well as the effective use of health-improving forms of education in educational institutions. The result is the formation of physical development.

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